

Development of monitoring techniques for coatings applied to industrial heritage

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Abstract

This paper presents a new approach for the evaluation of the preventive properties of outdoor protective coatings against corrosion as applied to industrial heritage. The approach relies on the combination of three different analytical techniques: Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), FT-IR Spectroscopy and Microscopy (both Scanning Electron- and Optical-Microscopy).

This work focuses on the preliminary results obtained by EIS carried out with a specially designed contact probe suitable for in field studies on art bronze objects. This measurement method was tested on steel coupons (pre-corroded and on original painted steel), prepared during the CONSIST project¹ and protected with different transparent organic coatings in order to compare the effectiveness of their protective behavior after a period of natural aging. The EIS testing procedure is relatively simple and gives quantitative data about the performance of the protective coatings. Nevertheless, the acquired spectra have been interpreted, at present, from a qualitative point of view. The results for the samples before and after exposition allow to distinguish different corrosion behaviors and to describe protective coating failure. Further measurements are on its way; these will aim at achieving a better understanding of the role of iron corrosion products in the protective behavior of organic coatings.

Although still at a preliminary stage of the project, the results described in this work show the potential of the EIS technique for the aimed purpose, our ideas in adapting it to the monitoring task and our efforts to combine it into a practical tool in Conservation Science. Preliminary results are reported.

Keywords: Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy, EIS, Industrial Cultural Heritage, steel, iron corrosion, corrosion protection, organic coating,

Introduction

The Industrial Revolution was not only the transition from manual production methods to new manufacturing processes relying in machines, but also the beginning of a historical phenomenon that has influenced a great part of the human population and almost every aspect

¹ Comparison of Conservation Materials and Strategies for Sustainable Exploitation of immovable Industrial Cultural Heritage made of Iron and Steel supported by the European Commission under the 6th Framework Program http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/74938_en.html

of daily life. This influence continues to the present day (Douet & International Committee for the Conservation of the Industrial Heritage 2012).

Industry gives identity to a region, as testimony of progress and development of society. In the years after the deindustrialization of large industrial sites in Germany and in Europe, a reawaken of a nostalgic feelings in the public opinion has taken place (Götz, Brüggerhoff & Tempel 2009).

“The material evidence of these profound changes is of universal human value, and the importance of the study and conservation of this evidence must be recognised” (International Committee for the Conservation of the Industrial Heritage 2012). An increasing need has appeared to “recognize” the historical and the authenticable value of industrial objects and plants as a witness that may be hand down to the future generation. Today, in accordance with the spirit of the Venice Charter (International Council on Monuments and Sites 1964), the intention to conserve and restore industrial heritage is to safeguard it rather as work of art than as only a historical evidence. The “Nizhny Tagil Charter” (International Committee for the Conservation of the Industrial Heritage 2012) defined industrial heritage as the “remains of industrial culture which are of historical, technological, social, architectural or scientific value. These remains consist of buildings and machinery, workshops, mills and factories, mines and sites for processing and refining, warehouses and stores, places where energy is generated, transmitted and used, transport and all its infrastructure, as well as places used for social activities related to industry such as housing, religious worship or education”.

Handling of industrial heritage is a rather new field within Conservation Science and there is still a lack of knowledge and guidelines both for conservation and evaluation of preservation measures (Brüggerhoff, Götz & Tempel 2014). The reason is the vastness content of industrial buildings and technical objects that does not fit in one single discipline. They range from small to huge structures featuring a great variety of materials. Industrial sites were never planned to stay permanently, especially due to the nature of the materials which they were made of. During their active life, they are be protected in order to guarantee their function over a long enough period, but this measures are stopped as soon as the industrial plant is shut down.

In nature, iron is only present in the form of compounds in higher oxidation states and never in metallic form. In fact, metallic iron has a high tendency to return to the form of its more stable oxides thus giving rise to corrosion. Iron has a high tendency to corrode and it is very difficult to make a long-term preservation modelling even under a given set of environmental conditions (Scott & Eggert 2009). Therefore the “definition of goals” is the most important part of the conservation process, because it needs to develop a compromising approach through an interdisciplinary working group. The constant exposition of surfaces made of iron and steel to the rain or moisture makes the use of conventional corrosion protection theoretically necessary. Conventional treatments start with sand-blasting until a clean metal surface is achieved. A multiple pigmented coating system as anti-corrosion protection is applied at the end with a long-term stability of at least 15 years (according to DIN EN ISO 12944). Is this really necessary? In this way, we lose the original surface; the treatment erases every kind of usage marks including part of the historical character of the object.

However, when choosing coatings as conservation treatments, other properties are often considered: coatings should be transparent (visual appearance), removable (reversibility) and they should not modify the material of the original artefact (legibility). Comparing with industrial multi-layer systems, the use of transparent organic-polymeric coatings fulfilling the above mentioned conditions obviously increases the need of maintenance.

The preservation of traces of daily use and handling in order to keep the original appearance has relevance on its own. This evidence of former activities has a “universal value (...) rather than on the singularity of unique sites”. Equally important is also the social value as “part of the record” of the daily lives of “the masses of ordinary people”. This impact, coming from

the Industrial Revolution, contributes to the emergence of an important sense of identity (International Committee for the Conservation of the Industrial Heritage 2012). In this kind of “works of art” we cannot speak literally of aesthetic value because this obviously does not reside in how the objects appear but in how the industrial technology assumes a symbolic value from the society which, in some ways, has influenced their lives.

It is very important to understand *what* and also *how* must Industrial Heritage be preserved for future generations. During the period that passes from the shutdown or end of the active life of a site until its recognition as a monument of cultural significance, several years of dilapidation may occur. Vandalism and the heavy damages appearing as a result from the weathering processes (increasing rust formation that destroys the objects within a few years) are the main reasons (Götz, Brüggerhoff & Tempel 2009). Therefore the preservation of the state of decommissioning (i.e. the time when the plant was closed) is hard to achieve because it is not always possible but it is fundamental to assure to the best of our ability that its condition remains unchanged. The historical and authentically state have the priority. The whole range of different levels of information must be identified, recorded and protected for future generations.

Obviously, in the restoration of industrial monuments and sites (for the technical objects too) many treatments are possible and they must be carefully considered because they can often modify the appearance of the object and with it the point of history that is intended to be preserved. Therefore, it is important that the interventions should be reversible (better re-treatable) and have a minimal impact. Knowledge of how conservation materials age, how they interact with the object and how the object responds to its environment are a fundamental prerequisite. According to the Venice Charter (Article 10), “(...) the consolidation of a monument can be achieved by the use of any modern techniques for conservation and construction, the efficacy of which has been shown by scientific data and proved by experience”. Scientific know-how and pertinent research studies are extremely important in order to establish the effectiveness of the conservation treatments. Their properties must be examined, interpreted and evaluated upon ageing in order to better understand the long-term resistance and stability. Artificial weathering methods in climate chambers are very useful for the first test phase of the coatings but measurements made “in situ” (indoor or outdoor), in naturally aged material, is the best measure of their effectiveness. The outdoor environment cannot be exactly reproduced inside a laboratory and therefore it is indispensable to establish a “best practice guide” able to allow this kind of evaluation by means of portable analytical instruments. The in-situ conservation of metallic surfaces is a scientific challenge and the characterization of their condition is essential to estimate the progress of atmospheric corrosion on the metal (Angelini et al. 2014).

A monitoring strategy is therefore needed for the quantitative evaluation of the condition of transparent coatings and their effectiveness in protecting the metal surfaces against corrosion. A precise approach instead or besides visual inspection has to be developed to guarantee an early information on coating failure. Our approach is based on three different analytical techniques. Firstly, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), which has proved to be effective for evaluating the protection efficiency of coatings. EIS provides information about corrosion rate and mechanism occurring at the metal/coating interface even when no corrosion product is yet visible. This methodology was adapted to be directly applicable for coating characterization on cultural heritage in field studies (Letardi et al. 2000). Secondly, FT-IR Spectroscopy will be used to both identify the coating and to follow its degradation by studying the chemical changes in the polymeric structure upon aging. Finally, Microscopy (both Scanning Electron- and Optical-Microscopy) will allow analysis of structure and defects of the coating layer (cracks, detachment etc.) and of the metal/coating interface (corrosion products). This paper focuses on EIS measurements, with the specially designed contact-probe cell (Letardi & Spiniello 2004), for the study of transparent protective coatings applied

on steel substrate with different surfaces (pre-corroded and painted) aged under natural environmental condition.

Experimental details

For this preliminary tests, metal coupons were selected from a wide range of samples prepared during the CONSIST project supported by the European Commission under the 6th Framework Program from 2005 to 2008. The samples have been preserved until the present day in the laboratory under a controlled atmosphere inside a desiccator. In order to identify both the role of the substrate and of natural aging on the protective properties of coatings for outdoor industrial monuments, both pre-corroded and original painted steel coupons were chosen for the analyses. As the samples have been stored for a pretty long time, the results may not fully reflect the behavior of freshly prepared ones; this is not a real problem in this study which mainly aims at checking the potentiality of the contact-probe EIS measurements for the monitoring technique under development.

Two sets of samples cut into pieces of 10 x 5 cm were selected:

- Unalloyed steel (DC 04 B – EN 10130, Franz Krüppel, Krefeld – D) pre-corroded in a standardized manner (Seipelt, Pilz & Kiesenberg 1998).
- Original painted steel parts from the mine in Riedel (Germany).

The list of samples used for this preliminary test is show in Table 1.

Some coupons were coated. Four protective coatings were chosen: a micro-crystalline wax (Cosmoloid H80), an oil based coating (Owatrol), an organo –silane coating (Ormocer B30) and a polyurethane (EK-PUR). The coating products were brushed as a single layer on the chosen test coupons. The natural aging was conducted in a chamber of the demonstration mine of the Deutsches Bergbau-Museum in Bochum where the samples, placed in a test rack, were exposed for six to seven months. At a temperature of approximately 15°C and an ambient humidity of approximately 100%.

The EIS measurements were performed with a portable USB potentiostat/galvanostat/ZRA configuration (Gamry Reference 600, Framework+EIS300 software v6.25, Gamry Instruments, Inc.) and the contact-probe setup (Letardi 2000) as shown in Fig. 1.

The contact probe ST15 was designed for in situ measurements on bronze monuments; it is made of AISI 316L Stainless Steel Reference (REF) and Counter Electrode (CE) mechanically inserted in Teflon (PTFE) (see insert in Fig.1). The probe area is 1.77 cm². The electrolyte chosen for these EIS measurements was a 10x concentrated artificial rain solution (Bernardi et al. 2008) (electrical conductivity 145 μS/cm², pH=5.07) because of its similarity to atmospheric humidity. To simulate an electrolyte layer, a commercial glass cleaning cloth soaked with the artificial rain was fixed to the contact probe to keep the electrolyte between the sample (the Working Electrode – WE) and the contact probe (Letardi & Spiniello 2004; Letardi 2001).

Table 1: List of samples considered in this preliminary test.

Test Coupons	Coating	Weathering	Label	Sample
Pre-corroded Steel specimens (DC 04 B)	Bare	Reference	SPR	330
		Demonstration Mine (M)	SPM	341
	Cosmoloid H80	Reference	SPC	5148
		Demonstration Mine (M)	SPM	253
	Owatrol	Reference	SPW	5292
		Demonstration Mine (M)	SPWM	225

Test Coupons	Coating	Weathering	Label	Sample
	EK-PUR	Reference	SPE	5265
		Demonstration Mine (M)	SPME	249
	ORMOCER B30	Reference	SPOB	5247
		Demonstration Mine (M)	SPMOB	233
Original Paint	Bare	Reference	SO	1 – 2
		Demonstration Mine (M)	SOM	337
	EK-PUR	Demonstration Mine (M)	SOME	27 – 28/31 – 32

Figure 1 - Cell setup for electrochemical measurements: contact cell developed for EIS measurements on artworks (Letardi 2013).

The EIS spectra were acquired about 30 to 40 min after the cell was fitted on the measurement area of the sample, in order to stabilize the open circuit potential E_{OC} . It is necessary to wait enough time for the system to reach an equilibrium such that the variation of E_{OC} is not greater than the excitation voltage over the time needed for measurement (Letardi 2000). Spectra with 10 points per decade were acquired in potentiostatic mode with 10 mV AC signal level at E_{OC} in order to perform non-destructive measurements (Letardi et al. 1999). Spectra were acquired in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 10 mHz. In these conditions the acquisition time is about 20 – 25 minutes. On the bare pre-corroded steel coupons a couple of measurements have been extended in the low frequency to 1 mHz as highly reactive surfaces require to go to lower frequencies to approach the Polarisation Resistance R_p ; the acquisition time in this case increased drastically to more than 1 hour and the measurements became more problematic. The wet footprint of the EIS contact probe on samples was photographed with a graph paper as background immediately after measurement in order to normalize data for the active measurement area, which is influenced by surface wettability.

As a quick comparison parameter, the value of the Impedance modulus $|Z|$ at low frequency was adopted. The $|Z|_{f=10\text{mHz}}$ value has been widely used as a parameter to compare the effectiveness of protective coatings: the higher the $|Z|_{f=10\text{mHz}}$ value the lower the corrosion rate of the superficial layer and consequently, the higher its protective effectiveness against the natural environment (Ercoli et al. 1999; Letardi & Luciano 2007).

The EIS spectrum acquisition has been repeated two to three times on each sample and after each measurement the samples were rinsed with de-ionised water and dried at room temperature.

Results and discussion

The EIS spectra acquired on the bare pre-corroded steel coupon (SPR330) compared with the ones measured on coupon aged in the demonstration mine (SPM341) are shown in Figure 2a as Bode diagrams (impedance modulus and phase). On the Reference coupon the acquisition has been repeated four times and in the aged one three times. Three and two different areas of the surface have been selected and analyzed respectively. On both samples, the measure was repeated in one area in order to observe the stability of the system in open circuit potential (fluctuation before and after the measurement) and the tendency to build new corrosion products.

Spectra on the sample SPR330 (Fig 2a - full symbol) show a high variability in the low frequency range, with up to one order of magnitude between measurements acquired in two different areas (SPR1 and SPR2). Measurements on the sample SPM341 (empty symbol) are much similar to each other. The resulting variability of the results shows in the above Bode plot, confirm how the various electrochemical processes play a different role in the different considered area (poor patina homogeneity). More spectra have to be measured on several sample areas and more coupons, in order to investigate homogeneity and repeatability of results (Feliu Jr., Morcillo & Feliu 1995).

Figure 2 - a) Bode plots of EIS spectra recorded onto different areas of the bare pre-corroded samples (see table 1 for sample labels): reference (full symbol) and aged (empty symbol). b) Photo of the sample SPM341 after the EIS measurements with the investigated area.

A deeper analysis of the system under investigation is required to fit the data with appropriate equivalent circuits. Nevertheless, the impedance modulus at low frequencies about $1\text{K}\Omega\text{cm}^2$ for the reference sample and even less for the aged one indicate a high corrosion rate. Where the measure have been repeated and the contact cell stay longer in contact with the surface, at the electrolyte/oxide surface/atmosphere interface (around the cell boundary) new corrosion products have been build (see fig. 2b - SPM2rip). Especially on oxide surfaces containing ferrous ions, the kinetics of the electron transfer reaction can be very fast and consequently the rate of the oxygen reduction (Scott & Eggert 2009). Iron have high tendency to corrode and so the corrosion can proceed very fast (Shreir 1995).

Figure 3 - Bode plot of Impedance spectra obtained on pre-corroded coupons with different coatings (labels in table1): a) not exposed b) aged (demonstration mine).

The impedance spectra obtained on coated pre-corroded reference and aged coupons are shown in Figure 3. All the spectra show the typical shape of coatings with a more or less protective ability. For each coating and weathering time two measurements have been acquired. On reference samples the two measurements are pretty similar, apart for Owatrol (orange plot) and Cosmoloid H80 to a lesser extent (in this case the phase shape suggest possible effects of normalization area uncertainties). On aged coupons quite a large difference in corrosion protection efficacy is obtained for the EK-PUR coating on the two measurement area.

In figure 4 the average $|Z|_{f=10\text{mHz}}$ values for all the coatings considered in this work are summarized. Before ageing the microcrystalline wax (Cosmoloid H80) has a value around $6\text{K}\Omega\text{cm}^2$, the organic-inorganic coating Ormocer B30 value is more than double higher (around $13\text{K}\Omega\text{cm}^2$) while the oil based coating (Owatrol) is two order of magnitude higher than the Cosmoloid H80.

The polyurethane (EK-PUR) shows the best protection. The Bode plot (fig 3a - neon green line) show a pure capacitive behavior with extremely high impedance at very low frequencies with $|Z|_{f=10\text{mHz}} = 85\text{G}\Omega\text{cm}^2$.

Figure 4 - Low frequency values of the impedance modulus $|Z|_{f=10\text{mHz}}$ for the coatings applied on pre-corroded steel coupons not exposed (reference) and aged (demonstration mine).

Cosmoloid H80 and Ormocer B30 show non meaningful differences after six month in the demonstration mine. The Owatrol $|Z|_{f=10\text{mHz}}$ value decrease one order of magnitude instead. Quite a sharp decay is shown by the polyurethane, (EK-PUR), with the $|Z|_{f=10\text{mHz}}$ falling down more than two orders of magnitude.

The comparison of Bode plots on reference and demonstration mine samples (figure 3) also enlighten very clearly the smooth evolution in corrosion protection for Cosmoloid H80 and Ormocer B30, the reduction in Owatrol and the Polyurethane sharp decrease. As already mentioned, it is also remarkable the huge difference between the two spectra obtained onto the same sample (Figure 5). The straight neon green line (Figure 3 - SPME1rip) is the result of the measurement acquired the day after, were the contact cell stay fixed for 16 hours over the night. In this way the electrolyte had more time to reach the coating/oxide layer interface. The resulting spectra show the same trend to the one acquired in the second area (SPME2).

Figure 5 - Photo of the sample SPME249 after the EIS measurements with the investigated area.

The impedance spectra recorded on the bare original painted steel are shown in Figure 6.

Two samples which were not exposed (figure 6b- coupons 1 and 2) have been measured at the center both on the front and back side in order to sample the EIS response of the original painted surface. On the sample aged in the demonstration mine (Figure 6b - coupon 337) two measurements have been acquired on different areas of the upward exposed surface.

The spread of results obtained in the Bode plot (Figure 6), enlighten the high sensitivity of EIS measurements to the electrochemical processes which play a role in the corrosion protection of coatings. The area SO2a, with a visible compact paint layer, is characterised by an impedance spectra typical of barrier coatings. The phase at high frequencies is not far from the -90 value of a capacitive behaviour and the measured $|Z|_{f=10\text{mHz}}$ value is $2.0\text{M}\Omega\text{cm}^2$ that suggest a compact layer with good barrier properties. Even area SO1a shows a high $|Z|_{f=10\text{mHz}}$ value ($1,56\text{M}\Omega\text{cm}^2$) but the impedance spectra suggest underneath electrochemical processes. In this area a very small painting failure (corrosion spots) is present: so the water can so penetrate into the coating through the pores and form a new liquid/metal interface beneath the coating.

Figure 6 – a) Bode plots of EIS spectra obtained on bare painted steel specimens (see table 1 for sample labels): references (full symbol) and aged (empty symbol). b) Photo of the samples with the investigated area.

The SO1b area (into the back of sample 1) shows a heavy damaged paint layer characterized from corrosion products and detached areas. The recorded impedance spectrum, has the lowest impedance value at low frequency, with a near pure resistive phase behaviour all over the spectrum. The other back side area SO2b (on sample 2) shows a more compact paint layer instead. The spectra obtained on the aged coupon also represents two different situations: on area SOMa small defects are visible and the EIS spectra is in between the ones measured on the reference coupons; on area SOMb the paint layer has a very good appearance and the EIS spectrum gives a better corrosion protection than the one measured on reference coupons. Obviously for these samples with highly uneven surfaces a larger number of measurements would be required (Feliu Jr., Morcillo & Feliu 1995) for a detailed analysis of the remaining paint layer film, which was outside the scope of this preliminary work.

Figure 7 show the impedance spectra acquired on the original painted steel coupons coated with polyurethane (EK-PUR) and aged in the demonstration mine; two different samples have been measured (Fig. 7b). One spectrum has been acquired at the center of each sample both on the upward (SOME3, SOME4) and bottom side (SOME1, SOME2) surface during exposure. Unfortunately no reference sample (painted steel coupon coated with EK-PUR not

exposed) was available to compare the performance of the transparent protective layer upon weathering.

Figure 7 - a) Bode plots of EIS spectra obtained on aged painted steel specimens coated with EK-PUR (see table 1 for sample labels). b) Photo of the polyurethane (EK-PUR) coated samples with the investigated area. The left side corresponds to the front of the sample while the right side corresponds to the back

The bottom side areas are characterized by the highest impedance value. The spectra show a typically capacitive behavior of effective coatings. The measured impedance values at low frequency are above $10\text{G}\Omega\text{cm}^2$. The upward areas show quite lower impedance values, in the range of the ones obtained on the bare original painted steel coupons (fig. 7a). As already enlightened, the high degree of unevenness of the original painted steel surfaces - with areas with well preserved paint to completely rusted zones - would require a larger set of measurements both on bare and treated surfaces before and after weathering. Nevertheless, measurements both on pre-corroded steel coupons and on original painted steel samples suggest a very quick degradation of the initially high corrosion protection of the EK-PUR.

Conclusion

The contact-probe EIS method showed good results to characterize the quality of coating applied on steel coupons of interest in the conservation of Industrial Heritage. The measurement setup adopted allows for a non-invasive surface analysis and can be used in situ also for non-destructive investigations on Cultural Heritage. The great variability of the results confirm how the morphology and the adhesion of the protective coating to the corrosion layer and on his part to the metal surface play a different role in the different

considered areas. Porosity and cracks on the coating layer can also be evidenced by EIS measurements. Therefore a deeper analysis is necessary for better understanding the composition, the morphology and the corrosion behavior of historical industrial surfaces and possible protective treatments. This preliminary measurement campaign, enlighten the needing for a proper statistical evaluation with sufficient data. A deeper characterization both on site and on coupons would be required in order to investigate homogeneity and repeatability of results. Although still at a preliminary stage of the project, the results described in this work shows the high potential of the EIS technique for the aimed purpose. EIS is certainly a good complementary technique to the other analytical methodologies considered in our evaluation approach. SEM observations and FTIR (maybe μ -Raman) would provide useful information; on one side to investigate chemical nature of the corrosion products layer and on the other to investigate coating failure and chemical degradation. Laboratory studies are advisable in order to fit these results to real conservation problems and maintenance strategies.

The goal of this research activity is to combine and adapt the selected analytical techniques into a practical tool for a monitoring task aimed at a better conservation practice.

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Cristian Mazzon born in Motta di Livenza, Italy, in 1982. He studied chemistry for the conservation and restoration of works of art at the University of Ca'Foscari in Venice. Since May 2014, he started his doctorate study at the "Deutsches Bergbau-Museum" (German Mining Museum) in Bochum, Germany, in the Section of Material Science. His work includes corrosion and protection of metallic surfaces with transparent organic coatings applied on Industrial Cultural Heritage and to develop a monitoring strategy into a practical tool for better conservation practice, i.e. monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness properties of protective coating under natural aging.

Paola Letardi has a degree in Physics and worked in the field of Material Science and Surface Spectroscopy, with a particular interest in the development of methodologies and instrumentation. She has acquired expertise in electrochemistry and developed the application of Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) to monitor in situ the properties of patina and protective coatings on bronze artefacts of historic and artistic interest. She is active in national and international projects on diagnostics and monitoring for the conservation of Cultural Heritage. Her research is focused on the study of corrosion of metals in the marine environment and on specific applications of electrochemical and spectroscopic techniques in the field of artifacts of historical interest.

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